

10:00 - 11:30	Session 5: Data Science for Astropysics in the Roman Era	Chair: Arianna Cortesi (Observatorio Do Valongo)
10:00 - 10:30	5a Invited Talk: Eric Gawiser (Rutgers)	Astrophysical Data Science in the Roman Era
10:30 - 10:45	5b Sidney Lower (Univ of Florida)	Ground-Truthing SED Fitting Methods in Galaxy Observations
10:45 - 11:00	5c Sankalp Gilda (Univ of Florida)	mirkwood: SED fitting for the twenty first century
11:00 - 11:15	5d Lorenzo Zanisi (Univ of Southampton)	A deep learning approach to quantitatively compare the fine stellar morphology of simulated and real galaxies
11:15 - 11:30	5e Marc Huertas-Company (IAC)	Making Discoveries with Generative Models in the Era of the Nancy Grace Roman Space Telescope

Session 5 live captioning on Wednesday, 7 October 2020

Max: Welcome back, everybody. Sorry for the delay there. I was struggling to begin the broadcast and also have live streaming to Facebook. If one of the other organizers could verify that we are streaming to Facebook. For some reason it was bumpy this morning. Anyway, I would like to welcome back everybody to our conference. I have two quick announcements. My name is Max Mutchler, I'm a member of the local organizing committee and, first I want to remind everybody over on slack we have our code of conduct which we ask you to review. Also on slack is where there is a separate channel for every talk where you will be typing in your questions and we will be reading them for you to the presenters. Also, all the posters are over on slack. One thing we are going to do today, you may have noticed, 11:30 Eastern time we have posters and discussion. And then a break. We actually prepared some slides of each of the poster titles, authors, and abstracts. We will be looping them through the break. Just to give you another way to peruse through the posters. I would like to turn it over to our session chair this morning to introduce our first speaker. I'm going to work on the streaming to Facebook which I understand is not working. Anyway, let me turn it over to **Arianna Cortesi** and we will get started. Go ahead.

Arianna: Good morning, everyone. I am Arianna Cortesi. It is my pleasure to chair the session in the Roman era. Our first speaker is **Eric Gawiser**. He's a professor in the Department of physics and astronomy at Rutgers University. He's going to tell us about the science in the Roman era. This talk is 25 plus minutes and I will give you a warning. Thank you.

Eric: Thank you, Arianna. I will speak about astrophysical data science in the Roman era and I really enjoy this picture of Nancy Grace Roman with an early model of the Hubble space telescope. Those of you who know me and notice how I tweaked the title will not be too surprised to see the next picture I show you. This will not be a talk about the data science of aqueduct, nor a rant about the usage of Roman numeral's and astrophysics. Why would you pick a system that has zeros? Enough. Data science and astrophysics, I teach that as a semester long seminar. There's just so much going on. I promise it won't be my standard colloquium. It would be cruel to fit 45 slides into 25 minutes. Unfortunately it won't be exhaustive, I want to issue a blanket apology to fans, to those who are doing excited

research, feel free to post the latest references and comments on the slack thread to this talk. Finally I've learned from all the campaigns and terms of the spin they use before the debate start that you should try to set expectations as low as possible. Hopefully that will be too pessimistic. I will try to do that. I will describe opportunities presented by the monstrous data volumes available with the Roman Space Telescope. I will mark those with a nice Roman insignia and introduce methods that may prove useful when designing community surveys with Roman, perhaps overused insignia, and note some research ideas that might interest some of you that are still needed in order for us to take full advantage of the revolutionary data. Let me start off by talking about a topic dear to my heart which is spectral energy distribution. It has been shown that we can use ultraviolet through near infrared, broadband, not just for that, but simultaneously reconstructing star formation history. And it's also been shown that that leads to better parameters in addition to constraining the star formation with a single parameter, that was never a very welcome parameter. Particularly looking forward to Sidney's talk that will follow my own, presenting her excellent results. Using these approaches we can seek physical, nonparametric, basically smooth curves that look like the history simulated for galaxies. They are not completely smooth, they have excursions and we can hope to reconstruct that as well, at least in the ensemble. We would like to use the method so that the number of features can increase with the data quality. That is something that is been achieved by the dense method. In a recent paper, he's at the University of Toronto, but did his PhD at Rutgers with me before that. You will notice that I'm willing to use, just like the 24 hours news channels too often, this breaking news insignia to mark something that is up to one year old. Let me talk a little bit about the method. We saw a flexible, marking the star at which time us at which the certain fractions formed. That's a set of Texas parameters or T50 would be the stellar mass being formed and then the history is described with stellar mass, like the integral, the most recent derivative and that. The galaxy and process become a very active, very data science allows us to create smooth histories that satisfy those at integral restraints. A flexible number of parameters that allows us to see the precision of the data quality is good enough which is the best definition of a nonparametric method. And this can be incorporated into any fitting coat if you're interested and trying it out, please check out the website. Here is just a picture with a particular star formation history, what we mean by t_{25} , when they first formed using one of the histories from Somerville, the model. T50 they formed, t_{75} , you get the idea. Again, you can see how this goes. If we are using those three parameters here we set these constraints and then the galaxy immediately gives us a smooth curve that meets those constraints, like this one. If we are fighting a star formation history, that is what the galaxy process with the particular function will choose. Of course we don't do the history space because the data doesn't tell us that answer. A key part of the method we have developed is to show through validation against simulation that when we get a good high square in the space between the true input, realize the broadband and what we are able to reconstruct, we are getting a good correspondence to the history space. That is what gives us the confidence that applies to real data. The leg gray curves here are draws, we use those to set uncertainty range around the star formation history at each point in time. And finally the ability to find an optimal number parameter is done by criteria which for the given tells us when the improvement is justified for adding more parameters. We can do that on a galaxy by galaxy basis. Let's come back to this list of things we can do for distribution in the Roman era, it enables trajectories, on the familiar star formation rates stellar mass diagram I've turned out here, three dimensional diagrams versus time in the figure is actually taken from the 20T paper. You can 50 galaxies and any observed and draw back in time. It allows us to learn where galaxies were at an earlier time and how they're moving, how much time they spent on the sequence versus above and below it. All sorts of exciting new science. As well as effectively expanding the volume because we were actually sampling outside of our cone when we serve galaxies and extrapolate them back with the star formation history reconstruction. In terms of what Roman can offer us, the it can be done to measure the star formation history. I'm thinking in particular of the density methodology that has been described in recent papers. And by comparing observed, our densities, basically the amount of variation on every possible timescale, with prediction galaxy simulation we can then constrain different impacts that is occurring in the Galactic. The cutting-edge astrophysics. I think that's an interesting idea, but the disclaimer is that these ideas, like advice or worth what you pay for them. There is a reason it says free on the set of bulbs. Make what you will. While we are talking about that, let's point out that this capability enables and a slightly more traditional way that the instantaneous star formation rate for very large galaxies. Here's a figure led by a grad student and we want back and we re-examined this modern flexible stellar population synthesis model and reconstructed the timescales finding that it's less than ten mega years, five many years to timescale, where the ultraviolet rate, the broadband is most sensitive to our 100 mega years, 200 mega years to the near ultraviolet. When we put those together in that paper, and to a first indicator we did the log of the ratio of the instantaneous, near instantaneous measurement, five mega years, over that closer to the 200 timescale. End of that is to short timescale in timescale history. In order to interpret this we did an extensive set of mock catalogs of star formation rate, the long timescale versus the HL for the nearest continuous.

In the published paper for predictions, added now, the main stream here is when things changed when we add the flux limit. And then at expected observational noise. And so what you can just see visually is that Roman capabilities are comparable to those, this broadens out because it's a larger sample. Of course not as deep as the James telescope. However, this comparison doesn't give you the full story because, I don't like to invite you come out one of these things is not like the other. The area covered with the spectroscopy is monstrous compared to these others, the existing that is even on a plot, orders of magnitude. This opens up some tremendous data science from the shared volume of objects we will be able to study. And if you put the comparison into a table you will see the flux limit of Roman is comparable to that. Shallower at redder part. One of the Roman planning papers points out that we will get 2 million for every month of the survey. That enables you to split the sample, the subsamples to conduct studies a function of the galaxy properties. Such as red shift, stellar mass, morphology, size, star formation rate. Another topic I wanted to mention was studying galaxy clustering. In order to determine the dark matter halo, to much better understanding of galaxies to the understanding we get from cosmological simulation. The figure that I've included here shows the evolution of clustering bias. This is a prediction figure for LSST, what they can achieve just what he galaxies by percentile in color. The red galaxies evolved, the blue involved, imagine relatively narrow. With Roman we can do similar analysis, but breaking up the large galaxy samples, and sometimes having that available. Even when were just doing the functions in the red shift, there is no improved that all G.E. available we can account for the probability that each expected galaxy is when we have a single emotion line, alpha versus an interval. Or when we put the galaxies and been won versus has been two or three. That is a paper, she completed her PhD at Rutgers this past summer and is now a doctoral fellow at the University of Michigan. You can also estimate the probability distribution for single mission detection, from the luminosity function of the galaxy. And so that's another way to get a probability to incorporate into the improved clustering method. When we have three dimensional information from redshifts we can do three dimensional. The redshifts are single emotion lines as will sometimes happen, but thankfully not too common. You can still use the probability of which line you think it ends and it's account for the contamination. There is a nice paper on this method led by Henry. And the idea I wanted to offer here, that I think is intriguing is to take recent work done at red shift is zero, breaking the star formation diagram and to galaxies above come on, and below the star-forming sequence. This is a paper by Berti. We can identify the star formation diagram that identify even more subsets than even those three groups. Go ahead and use the measured over SED from the analysis to see if it's true that the galaxies before the star-forming sequence are more massive and an over dense regions versus those that are above the sequence. We can do that at money redshifts. We can think of a similar analysis. The last topic I wanted to really cover here is more about enabling data by getting the best possible data set that covers a huge number of galaxies. And my intuition says that with Roman, this typo here, with the Roman field we will want to actually begin and mediate between the survey and the ultradeep fields, that he spoke about in such nice detail. We can cover something like 100 square disease to an 80 magnitude of 28 and that will give us 100 million galaxies whose multi-wavelength will be better than you can achieve over thousands of square degrees because you lack the data and have greater depth even from Roman. And so I want to maximize the overlap with other instruments, particularly the observatory LSST, Euclid to make the most of these fields. That is difficult over 2,000 square degrees or so, but feasible over 100. It will require advance planning. In terms of possible locations for roaming deep fields let's look at where the Reuben observatory is putting its deep field paired using what is now called the survey with space and time, LSST. The main surveys that you can see you come with a deep drilling fields so cold occupy significant areas of the sky. They actually cover 40 square degrees before a field and 20 degrees more which is up in the air but also deeper imaging on some level there. They depths achieved and even the first year at LSST are really helpful, in particular what Roman does not offer us. The existing broadband data, state-of-the-art is Subaru strategic program, about 27. 28 in the first year. and r 29. Three of them, through particular survey called SERV. Another thing to talk about in terms of choosing these fields from the sky is the narrowband survey that is led by Sue. Here we will study emitters that register for .5, 3.1, and 2.4 using three new filters like you want to James Rose introduced at higher red shift wavelength. This will have some energy with Roman, particular redshifts where the Roman grism can detect lines including a set of useful lines at a redshifts of 2.4 or so. Brought wavelength coverage, combined spectroscopy. It also means they have gone through the exercise by identifying the most promising deep fields with optical broadband imaging available on the sky, the fields, Subaru fields, and one HETDEX field. This is almost eight millennium simulation, which means there is new volume and the sample sizes are staggering. Imagine how much bigger the samples can be with the full volume where you yourself as much as he narrowband filter. I know that money if you have thought about this, some of the talks are presenting some exciting science with Larch that, examples of objects like these. Here are the fields we came up with, restricted to the southern hemisphere so it's important to think about, and a northern fields, such as the other candle fields, the

agency can my deep fields, or the deep field north that rises to the same level of's inability for roaming deep fields. If there are what additional data do they need that we can start planning for now that applies to all of these. We should think about you and G data. You have 5 minutes. Thank you. Just to give you a sense of the field, there is an equatorial field at the subset where they will have full coverage with the optical spectroscopy. There is also coverage of the field. That is a 24 square degree field. That might be attractive or slightly larger. What if you want a single hundred square degree field? Something worth thinking about would be elongated, but you can connect and chest you one square degree right here with a fifth of an extension. These are the conversations I think we should be having because it takes long time to acquire the complementary data. And now because this we have access, that is quite valuable. And so that leads me to my conclusion. The first is that Roman offer such great survey capabilities, from a wide too deep to alter a deep, what complicated on deep-deep? It might be easier to ask what science can't do? A particular note, are high galaxies samples will increase by magnitude, enabling a wide range of new science including data science. I would advocate to choose the Roman deep fields as soon as possible in order to enable observing proposals for the expensive but the complementary data. It is clear that astrophysical data science is advancing rapidly. I will only had time today to talk about a few examples. There are other things that are fascinating that are going on such as work by John and Josh in the community telescope directly from their images, something that they do to high redshifts. This is good resolution. And self organize maps being applied to redshifts and beyond. Just to name a couple more. It's hard to extrapolate, but we should at least use the curve, such as the star formation histories when we are planning surveys. I think about what data quality will be needed and which set of filters to cover, probably all of them as deeply as we can. Isn't that always the answer? I want to predict for you that the photometric methods and clustering analysis that are becoming quite high precision and involves cosmological purposes today, particularly to learn about dark are going to become common in galaxy evolution study techniques in the Roman era. That is another example of things that we should take into account as we plan our surveys and make marks for them. If you put all this together you might get the impression that the Roman Space Telescope will dominate science in the coming decade. And that seems like it could be a bit too strong. I wanted to leave you by posing a question on whether the synergy with the other observatories will be strong enough to create, and I do apologize for this, fully Roman empire. Remember, as long as it's coherent, it's a success spirit thank you for listening and I'll be happy to take questions.

Thank you very much for the interesting and clear talk. We have two questions already. I just want to remind everybody listening that the questions, please use the slack channel so that we can read them off now. The first question is, we have three questions now. He is asking, in the star formation history, can you use the evolution and the galaxy population as an additional constrained to set the star formation histories to be consistent with the star formation?

That's an excellent point. We like to call it consistency and is one of the opportunities to really make sure that things are circular where they should be circular in these analyses. Doing this in detail is challenging. We don't have a publication on it yet because of course the selection, for instance if you're observing red shift, extrapolating it back almost all of those galaxies will not actually be in your observed sample. You have to take the small overlap and account for that to make sure if you've gotten the agreement or not. Of course that's its own own opportunity. Something I didn't mention, that means we are going to much lower map to galaxies at high redshifts. You can do the direct observation and that is the greatest improvement of that method. Thank you for thinking about that.

Thank you. The next question is from Andrea, I hope I'm reading the names correctly. Thank you for the talk. Do you include AGN, also if I understood correctly, when using simulated data, how does that compare with other code, for example?

Good. In the star formation history construction, we are not including AGN, we try to eliminate before we do that. In the discussion of power spectral density, the impact of age and is included and simulations and there is essentially a template that you can find that would say it is important. I think I'm answering two different questions there, but that is probably okay. In terms of the star formation history construction, we can get photometric data, but so far this is what we been able to do with the data alone. Very good data base with 14 on the candle speed. And we have compared it with other cones, starting with our own and with simpler star formation history. There is an ongoing history fitting comparison within the candle team that is using several codes including dense faces, code, and that. Look for something to come out in the near future.

Thank you very much. I think we have time for last question. I also see Max appearing. Okay. The final question, okay, another one appeared already from Benjamin. Do you think the deep field have to describe should be a part of the five tier or is that something that can be done in an extended region?

That's a great question. I think it's really important we do some of these fields and in the five-year mission. Otherwise you'd be missing a natural middle layer of a wedding cake of studies if you go only only ultradeep and only high latitude. You can certainly imagine that there is space for only say 40 square degrees of these fields in the primary mission and in the extended mission you want to turn that into 200. You have to look at what the right numbers are. I think it would be quite a missed opportunity to wait until after five years to do that.

Okay. Thank you very much for the talk. And the answers to the questions. I am pleased to have a look at the questions in slack, other questions that are appearing. We can move to our second speaker.

Now we are going to have five talks of 12 plus 3 minutes each. And our next speaker, now I can see you, hi. Our next speaker is **Sidney Lower** from the University of Florida. She is going to tell us about the methods and galaxy observation. Can you? Great. I'm going to give you a warning to minutes before the end of the talk.

Sidney: Thank you so much. Hi, everyone. I am Sidney Lower, a third-year graduate student at the University of Florida. I've been working on improving SED techniques with my advisor, along with extremely helpful collaboration. SED modeling has been one of my, I'm a third-year grad student, so it's essentially been the only thing I worked on thus far and it's been really rewarding, however, as fun as this project has been, it's really brought to light how even the most fundamental, robust, you know, estimates, that we sometimes take for granted, there is a lot of uncertainty in those estimates. And a lot of that has to do with this slide I'm showing here. This slide is showing essentially all of the components, you know, very brief overview. The components that are involved in SED modeling. You have things that probably have to do with galaxy evolution and things that have to do with stellar evolution. Stellar evolution, a huge Grab Bag of uncertainties and in itself, as you can see here just a couple, handful of the major uncertainties and stellar pop synthesis, courtesy of the doctor showing, you know, the wide range of techniques, processes that we don't understand about stars yet. I'm going to pretend that we do know this and focus primarily instead on these models having to do with galaxy evolution. And so that has something to do with star formation history, chemical evolution, continuation, and how those play together, correlate in the observed galaxy SED. And so we use SED modeling to infer galaxy properties. It's one of the primary methods is it has been shown, we get pretty good results. I want to highlight something, a couple of galaxy evolution relations. We have the star-forming sequence. We have galaxy stellar mass function. We have the medalists of the relation. These are familiar relations that we have and we understand their evolution. I want to point out the fact that these relations all evolve by a factor of two. However, I want to point out a parallel fact which is that it's been found that across the code there's remained a persistent and systematic factor of two uncertainties and solar masses in the ST modeling. We typically like to think that solar masses are the most robust quantities inferred from the fitting, yet if our uncertainties are at a level at a factor, I'm not sure how certain we can be about these evolutionary relations that we are seeing. And so, Eric Gawiser pointed this out in his talk, introducing the topic of star formation histories. I've been really interested in the particular star formation history models in hopes to may be pinpoint and get more accurate stellar mass estimates. I'm going to go a little, may be broader than the nonparametric definition that Eric provided and my definition for nonparametric is simply any model that does not explicitly assume a function of form through a star formation. Maybe this is best, the best way to see this is to contract with a typical parametric star formation history. On the right I'm showing the perimeter space by a delayed start formation history. Where you have star formations that peak at some time and then decline exponentially thereafter. Your star formation is down by this exponential decline. Unless, you know, you have sufficiently large signs, your star formation will decline exponentially without the perimeter. And in contrast with this, sitting on the left, it does not have a predefined shape. It's a bit more flexible. What I want to talk about today is using these new improved models, seeing if they actually do give us improved estimates from galaxy. What I did is I, the results using cosmological emulation. What I'm showing here is essentially how I modeled going forward from the stellar gas distribution from the stimulation for each galaxy. I ran 3D transfer follies galaxy is to produce SED's. I took them and ran the process backwards, but this time through the modeling. Here I used prospector and it has star

formation histories and I compared the star formation histories, I compared the results from each model to the essentially, can we knock down this factor of uncertainty? You know, focusing on the impact that of the assumed form of the star formation history has on the inferred galaxy property. Here is essentially the plot of my paper which is showing the inferred stellar masses compared to the true stellar masses. This is for about 1800 galaxies from the cosmological simulation. These were fit with four different star history models come every other model, maps, et cetera were the same across these models. The only thing that changed was the star formation model. What we can see from the plot is that the accuracy of our inferred stellar masses have improved quite a lot. Maybe that's easier to see here. Between the nonparametric in orange, the other three models, we see much greater improved accuracy just with the stellar masses. Showing the offsets between the true end to the inferred quantities. This is not really surprising. Eric Gawiser, many others have found that using a simple parametric form, because the star formation histories, biases the stellar mass that you get, even more than that, it also underestimates the true uncertainties of the quantity. And so what this is showing now is the fraction of galaxies where essentially the error bars are covering the truth value. And so what that means is that if a galaxy as a stellar mass that is over estimated or underestimated you would hope that the one bar on that stellar mass are large enough to cover the true stellar mass. In other words, we hope that the uncertainty covers the biases of each. And what we see broadly is that the parametric model do not do this at all. Only about 20% of the galaxies fit with a delayed component, have uncertainties that track the biases. Whereas the majority of galaxies with the nonparametric's see bars that track of these biases, these offsets. We can also look to other infer galaxy quantity. It's great that these models can and for the stellar mass accurately, but it's him a little bit meaningless if they cannot simultaneously infer he stellar ages and the star formation rates. What we see is that the nonparametric model of our, more accurate at simultaneously inferring essentially all galaxy property. And showing here, we can also reconstruct the star formation histories of these galaxies. Randomly chosen galaxies, we have the true star formation history and black and then the nonparametric in orange. The solid line is the median and then the shaded regions for each color are the one region. What we tend to see is that, 2 minutes? Yes. 2 minutes. Thank you. What we tend to see is where the delayed tends to mess with the median model has, it's essentially saying that all the perimeter space could work which is a very helpful. For trying to infer the galaxy property. One thing we did notice however is that for galaxies that have star formation, especially, I don't want to call it the birth because of how long of this star formation occurred, so essentially the early time is very hard to infer. This isn't just an issue with the nonparametric or the prospector, but it is a symptom of SED fitting. Because we are fitting this in the SED space and not star formation space, we have nonuniformed sensitivity to early variations, variations of the whole formation history. I'm cheating a little bit putting up the 2019 paper showing that, he also explored the concept that as we go back in time in the star formation history there is less and less evidence in our SED of that star formation. Early, star formation is dominated by the prior instead of the likelihood given in the SED. Through all of this I have kind of done a switch where I focused essentially on the star formation history, but I ignored that, which should maybe send the alarm in your head that these should be trusted, but my goal was to focus on the star formation history and see just how much of the stellar mass budget can be attributed to just the assumptions we made in the star formation history model. What I'm currently working on now is putting that into this. The results are shown, we fix the curve to the true curve, but now I want to ask the question, what happens when the continuation curve in the model are allowed to marry? And how do those results change and how can we improve upon those results? With that I put up my conclusion slide worm essentially saying that if you weren't convinced by Eric Gawiser's talk that the models should definitely be use in our next generation of data from the telescope, if you want to really pin down galaxy evolution, we have to nail down that first. Thank you.

Thank you very much for this interesting and fundamental talk. Your methods are very important to be explored and used. We have two questions. I'm going to list the first one from Marc Huertas-Company. He is asking, we stellar mass, where it is estimated, is?

I'm not sure on that. In our, we found that the parametric tends to underestimate the nonparametric slightly overestimate. I'm not sure if I can do it apples to apples with other studies because I ignored it, so that will contribute to the uncertainty budget certainly. I don't think I have a very good reason to say why this tends to be the case other than, especially with a delayed model, if it does not pick up on early star formation, like you see on the figure on the right. It's going to miss out on a lot of stellar mass. Whereas the nonparametric does not really suffer from that same issue.

That's great. There is another question which is actually a related question. Do you see a similar value with one sigma of the M model?

That's a good question. I assume you mean delayed and then we add a constant somewhere? I think. Yes. Adding 27% as in the case. Yeah. The constant is just across time. The only complication, not complication, but the only complexity we added to the model is adding the component. We saw that it didn't really do much for either the stellar mass or the uncertainty. We were a bit hesitant to add more and more complexity to functional forms because it's always going to be dominated by the functional form. We just want sure if adding further complexity to these models was worth it, especially when they nonparametric's, I didn't show it here, but the nonparametric has similar results for number of parameters anywhere from 4-12 I believe I tested. If you add more and more parameters to the parametric I'm not sure the payoff would be, would increase, the path that you get from me nonparametric. With the same number of parameters. Hopefully that answers it.

Because there are several other questions appearing in slack, so I think you will have a very good conversation there. If you want to follow-up and answer. Thank you again, Sidney.

We are going to move to the next speaker. They are here already. Hi appeared in our next speaker **Sankalp Gilda**. I hope I said it correctly. Also from the University of Florida. He's going to tell us about that for the 21st century. Your slides will appear I believe. I can't hear you. Arianna, I suggest we move onto the next speaker. We will try to get back to you. While you are sorting that out, and pleasure to have our next speaker. That is Lorenzo Zanisi. From the University of Southampton. He will tell us about the learning approach and compare the stellar morphology. I am going to give you a warning to minutes before the end of the talk. Thank you. He is speaking but we do not hear him.

We will go ahead to **Marc Huertas-Company**. He is currently on the Institute with the scholarship. He is going tell us about the discoveries with the models and the era of the Nancy Grace Roman Space Telescope.

Marc: Okay. Thank you very much. For giving me this slot. I hope, it's earlier than expected, I hope my kids don't run in the background, but anyway. I'm going to talk about how to use deep genetic models to detect. I want to acknowledge work from the people especially, Berta worked with me in Paris and Kate was a great student at NYU and we worked together a couple of summers ago. I think we all know that we become a data sets allow us to inspect all these data as we normally do. This is just an example as the surveys. One question that arises, how do we make discoveries? One of the big things that we have is I think we are seeing that these data sets, we process mostly automatically, probably a lot of ML methods. What happens is that most of the data will never be looked by humans. As opposed to carbon data sets. We still have a size where we can inspect many objects or at least have a global look at the data. No one knows, something we are not expecting, but this is where potentially it will be found. And if you look at the history of astronomy, many discoveries came by looking at an object. And that respect we need to tune to these automatic methods to find objects, what we call in the data science world, to detect anomalies. And it's crucial to reduce the sample size that we have to inspect with the discovery potential. Before I go to that I think the question is, what would be an anomaly? You think about these in a realistic way, the data follow some kind of distribution piece. Which depends on the space bar example, the imaging. An anomaly in that respect, we don't think that it has the distribution or data has... Okay. I was saying that once you have the distribution, so your data follows the distribution, so an object, anomaly, according to the PDF it should have a small -- to be observed. The point is how do you compute the distribution? And the answer is you can use deep genetic models, to learn from your data what is the density function of your data. And inside this box or this white box I put here, there is a bunch of different models which are called this, they allow you to estimate, networks and, for example all three models. These models have the capacity because of these networks to learn the PDF of the data. And once you learn you can generate quite realistic images. The ones I'm showing here from a recent paper. You see these images that are all fake, but our samples from of the PDF you learned from your data. By training on the data in a supervised way you learn the PDF and then you can sample realistic data. This is the idea we had to use these kinds of genetic models to learn. We use a particular genetic model, and entering into the details, basically this is what the model box, you learn basically the effects which is the output of this newer network settings. The idea is in order to test how this will work, to detect anomalies we trained the survey which is a survey at the telescope about -- it contains around 400 million

objects. The idea was to train on the survey which is not like Rome and because around, but the amount of objects, to see if we can identify, and a automatic way. We selected a smaller sample of these objects, I can go into videos of why. And once you have this then you can go for every detected object in your image and then ask what is the probability of these things you learn of observing the objects here? And then you can select and identify the objects and the distribution or whatever you like. In order to show you how these networks are able to generate the data, an example of what the model has learned. On the left you see the real agency images centered around objects, many of them are compact. And this is on the right, you see generated data by the networks. The network with the PDF, these are the images that generate mock images. So now what you want to do is you see what are the options? The way you do it, you see it estimated, we go object by object and ask what is the best you can do in particular? For that object, for every object we get the formation. We have real objects here on the bottom row, the best guest of the network on the bottom row you see this. Some objects that are normal and the network learned very well after we produce them, we have larger. In that way you can see the distribution of these anomalies switches and measurement, plus some other meters. And see how they are viewed there. Objects with very low anomaly scores which are on the left, maybe you don't want to look at them because they are very normal. Their money like that in the survey. It's not specifically. And then you have the high anomaly that could be an object that you might want to look at. You want to select the object, you can't reduce the data set. That is the one that the network is dragging for some reason to reproduce, evenly data was shown. This is an example of the objects that identified, increasing anomaly scores and you see the average galaxies are over here with more residuals, real constructive, and then the Sigma, you see some extended sources over here. And then over here, the systems that the network cannot reproduce. One thing you see immediately here and this is one typical problem of the detection is that you collect a lot of views what are not interesting for science, but our pipeline errors. The question is, how do you filter out interesting anomalies? On the one side you've already reduce the data set which is interesting. The number of objects you want to look at is smaller, but it's not that you are automatically finding the most amazing objects. We need something else to try to dig in and this is where you can use other data science and you can also start doing some inspection. In that particular case what we did is, okay, let's try now to look at the residual images. What are the typical or what some information about why. We use another network. And basically we have more, we try to explore these dimensions and how they populate the space. And see if you know, the objects that are there for one particular reason, to separate the errors for more interesting objects. If you see these dimensions you see that it's a plane you get and you see there's a clear correlation with anomalies. Anomalies, code residuals, they have some orders. They are close or for some reason, the lower our here. Now you can go and explore this and this is where again you need some kind of human intervention that you have produced a number of interesting objects. What I wanted to do here, but since I was earlier than expected I'm not sure if I will have time. I wanted to show you a demo of the spirit I'm not sure if it will work. Can you see? Yes. And you have 2 minutes. Okay. It's fine. You can project these three Sigma and then go and explore these objects. For example, you can see how they populate with anomalies and then you can go and see, okay, these have very high anomalies together. And then you go east and if it works, sorry, okay. It's always like that when you do a demo. Anyway, if you look at this group over here and you manage -- I don't know why, you can see the images. And then you can go scroll, what are the images in this particular group of objects? And then you can select the objects that might be interesting. In that way you are kind of reducing the data and you are specific targeting. Sorry that didn't work so well, but trust me, it works. I will go back to my talk. I will show you, I will end by showing examples of anomalies that we found by using the combination of model, for example the network found to these objects very blue and bright. And when you look at these you see and realize it's a galaxy interacting with another dwarf galaxy here. And this is a system that was recently discovered. An extreme star-forming dwarf. It is followed up already by another group. Our anomaly detector founded a weird object. We also found a bunch of objects which are very red that have some kind of blue off-center dots and resultant sources somewhere. The network found several of those, some of those have this imaging. You can see the objects, weird behavior here and it turns out to be a black hole which was pointed out and work galaxies. Also pointed out by this discovery. It is something the network found by itself. You see, they are some kind of centers, agent spirit some pulmonary examples of one of these objects. And the analysis is very preliminary, but you see that diagram, like AGN, but they are close. They have liens which can be, you know, outputs. I will stop here. I will say that, it was quick but I think you see the genetic models are I think an efficient way to detect anomalies in the astronomical surveys and it's important to unlock the surveys like Roman. I think they are a promising way to perform a blind search of interesting objects and larger surveys. The problem goes to how do you figure out boring anomalies. This is still challenging and I think this is where our astronomers need to become what we our input and you need some kind of degree of human input. And this is probably one of the ways to go. Thank you so much.

Thank you very much. Marc, especially doing the talk in advance. I'm going to QA quick question. And then I will -- several questions and slack appearing. Please afterwards have a look. Please reply. I'm going to read the question. Great to talk! How does this method of anomaly detection using this compare to anomaly detection techniques such as other reduction techniques?

Excellent question. I didn't have time to address it. For example, in the first paper we showed that as compared to PCAs for example, no anomaly such as these mergers of galaxies. It attacks some difference that we don't see in other linear demonstrated reduction techniques. Also for example, in case we try to directly apply the reduction in coder to a space, not the residual, and then the plastering is less obvious. The anomalies are not plastered. It outperforms in the sense that it's able to detect some subtle differences which probably are met by other moments that you can compute or damage the reduction. That's a good question.

Okay. Thank you very much. Please have a look at the slack. There are questions there for you. maybe we move on. Thank you, Mark. Thank you.

There we go. Nice to hear you. Okay. Our next speaker is **Sankalp Gilda** from the University of Florida. He is going to tell us about the SED fitting for the 21st century. I'm going to interrupt 2 minutes before.

Sankalp: Hi, again. I am Sankalp Gilda. I am presenting in collaboration with Sydney who spoke just a couple of speakers before me. And my advisor, we are calling it Mirkwood and the hope is it will phase out. What it is is basically machine learning plus astronomy, when you combine them we show that we get really good results. Let's start with a very high level review that is very important. For several reasons. It's the primary way to derive galaxy properties. We also know that the amount of data far surpasses the amount of data because of the constant. More often than not it's the first step in a long pipeline of scientific discoveries. It's very crucial to nail down galaxy parameters that derive, as well as you can. What is the problem? A few problems. One is its compute intensive. It is run on supercomputing notes. It takes several hours, actually it takes, when we did it on, about 10,000 galaxies, it took 2-3 days. Even though we get accurate results and I will show all of this through plots, and it doesn't take robustly into account different types of errors that exist. I will delve into that. Again, a quick recap. Compared nonparametric to parametric and she showed that at 50, the impact is quite gigantic depending on what transition you choose. You get drastically different results. What I'm going to show is using machine learning, even the current state-of-the-art nonstar formation history with the right parameters. Even down to a very low SNR of five. Just a quick reminder, something to keep at the back of your head, this is an SR of 50. Enter Mirkwood, what is it? As a machine learning based tool where we try our hardest to design a glass box and not a black box. The solutions that come out are explainable. You can relate the output you get and in a visual way. It's accounts for both systematic errors and statistical errors. It's fast, on my home computer which I have a 12 -- pretty regular one. I was able to run things in a matter of hours versus days on a supercomputer. And it significantly miraculous compared to traditional. People often think that machine learning is basically you have this box and you shall buy a bunch of stuff into it and outcomes, you know, magical results. That used to be the case up until a few years ago, but a lot of effort has been spent and is bent into making these models laid a bull. This no longer is the case. Things are moving at a very fast pace. The specific type of machine learning that I'm going to be using is called supervised ML. You have a bunch of inputs and outputs to train your model on and then you see an unknown sample that you haven't seen before and spits out a result and you compare that result to the result of the sample that you already know. For us the inputs will be 31 band for about 16,000 galaxies and Z equals 0.43 simulations. At least to a first-order averaging over different physics that goes into place we are going to be predicting work galaxy properties, maps, dust maps, medalists Eddie city and instantaneous star formation. I'm not going to spend a lot of time explaining how this pipeline works I would like to focus on the results but very quickly this is what the whole pipeline is. The parts to take note on his for each sample to offer three values, it outputs a -- it outputs two types of uncertainties per example. Quick description of what these uncertainties are. What we in astronomy usually refer to statistical versus systematic. A systemic uncertainty come uncertainties that are high in areas where your training sample is sparse for example if I show you my model on galaxies where it's below ten and I input a galaxy with 9-10 I'm a mess of galaxies, ideally what you would want your model to do Emma it would give you a better results, but a very high error. That type of uncertainty, the uncertainty. In

our case it occurs primarily because of the photon in the data. Also your input sample increases with the uncertainty. Here are some results. I'm very excited to present these results. I said we are predicting for galaxy parameters. Perimeter number one word on the x-axis, truth values on Y. These are plots of the means of our productions. You can see even as low as five we get extremely robust results. As compared to, you know traditional. On the Y and X marginal plots their marginal, so you see for example, here you would imagine they both overlap perfectly. When we produce results using traditional settings, you compute constraints, we didn't do it for all galaxies, about 12,000 or so and then these don't exactly match. That is just, it doesn't really affect the quality of our results. Three different metrics, this is normalized, and normalized error. Ideally, an ideal case they should all be zero. They can go as high as one or even higher. This is, as you can see, the contrast even quantitatively, the results are drastic. A similar plot for dust mess, same thing. Quality and quantity the results are drastically different. Metallicity and finally, instantaneous star formation rates. There we go. These are self-explanatory. I can talk more about this in a slack if you would like. That took care of the point predictions, to quantitative -- yes, quantitative analyze our error bars we introduced two different metrics. One is called the fraction of your true mass or true property within plus or minus, so here, we hear that, that mental, and this is necessary because if you have your function and you train your model and a way to an maximize fraction of true quantity within one Sigma, excuse me, a fraction of one quantity with true quantity. What the model could technically do it as it will say, I'm just going to make all of my error bars infinite and that should take care of things. That is not actually what you want to. What you want is for those error bars to be as tight as possible and yet to get in ideal of .6. That is the percentile or the fractional value within plus-minus. You have 2 minutes. Okay. Thank you. That takes care of -- these are complementary metrics and we see that, we improve compared to that, our results are significantly better. We use the technique called calibration, it's a little technical and I will not get into the details. It's basically take this as an input and it increases the robustness of the operation. It pushes these values higher. Finally, these are the value plots. Hear what we see, completely in the data-driven way are model is able to find important says. For mass and shows us at 1.98 microns. This is the most important band in predicting your mass pretty model completely outputs it. The way to reach this is as the feature value, and this case it is the flocks, as the future value increases, as you get more there, it will respond to a higher max atomic mass as it goes lower, it will respond to a low mass and as you can see, the most important, the H, we see this affects and spreads out which makes it dense. You need a little more information and a few more bands to capture the same kind of results. Similarly we get this result for dust mess, metallicity. It shows the band is most important and this is due to the famous mass metallicity relationship. I don't think this directly is about the fact that it's by itself, it's more -- it's important with a mask which we know is important to predict metallicity. And finally this is for star formation rate. Our paper is in progress. I will be doing this for like a month, hopefully, by the end of this month. If you have any questions feel free to ask on slack or email me. Thank you.

Thank you. Thank you for this great talk. There are several questions. I'm going to just read one part of the question. Asking, with missing data points -- okay.

Yes. The work that I show, the plot that I showed, there was no data at all, but radically it is trivial. And I'm reading the same part of that question. They ask, is it neuron based or forward? It's a machine model. There are no nuances. Your input uncertainties are propagated forward and the model is also able to account for its own intrinsic uncertainty. What it does is it says, these thousand samples which were original, what if we take 800. It is called bootstrapping, selecting randomly multiple times. This way by carrying out the analysis this way we are able to account for the air that originates because of the differences in the training data and differences in the parameters get covered.

Okay. Thank you very much. I encourage you to answer the questions so we can move to the next talk. Thank you.

Our last speaker is **Lorenzo Zanisi** from the University and he's going to tell us about a learning approach to compare the hydrodynamical simulations.

Lorenzo: Hi, I am Lorenzo. I am from the University of Southampton and I'm a PhD student there. Today I'm going to tell you something about some work that I started doing last summer at the program and astrophysics. I had a lot of help and insight from collaborators that are listed here, particularly from Marc Huertas-Company, and the whole team. I will just go into the talk. Obviously all of us know that there are a variety of galaxy morphologies out there and this is

a picture for example of the Hubble sequence which is something that you know didn't look like this. This is a picture. Until not so far ago, six or seven years ago, simulations were struggling to produce. With the eagle and many other simulations that didn't have time to go on the slide, but are equally important and useful, we have started seeing the simulations could come a they could reproduce galaxy morphologies in a variety of ways. The thing is, how exactly are these morphologies reproduced and how realistic are the very fine details? This is a very important question because we know that the galaxy morphology is set by galaxy physics. Different physical implementation. We really want to try to actually quantify this. So far the gold standard for doing this is the morphology. This is a way that's been around for a few years now and it's given us great insight, of mergers and so on. The problem with the morphologies is that they are assessed, a mathematical and they are, there may be some of these expressions that we are not taught about. So we would really like a new network to think about them for us in some way. Also these morphologies have provided separate pieces of information where we would like to see all of the galaxy morphology sometimes and only one value. I should note that there has already been done some work trying to compare the morphology of galaxies, that I'm aware, and we already got some insights from this. However we would like to go past of these approaches and try to generalize. The way we do this. The image, a skinny filter that goes all over the image and captures high ratios, and they are captured by the series of layers are stacked. They are then, they are then optimized and that hopefully the network will learn what it galaxy looks like and it will learn a finer correlation that may be in the previous approach. This is what I will set out now, unsupervised. We are really letting the network to everything for us here. We have a network that ideally takes in, observed galaxies during training and then it learns how they look like by minimizing the function. And then a test, sorry come a test time, we treat this problem as a detection problem. We take galaxies from simulations and we feed them to the network and hopefully the network will tell us, already have seen something like this with the observation I was trained on. It could also be that the next group could tell us, I've never seen the galaxy before so it must not be realistic. The network spits out one number, so we call it there. Obviously you can check out the paper if you want to know about the strategy a bit more in detail. I thought I would give you the blurb for the sake of time. We don't have only one image produced, we have a set of images, distribution. What you need to know for the rest of the talk is that it means a galaxy is more likely to be a outlier and a high LLR, this means that distribution of galaxies from observations with peak higher LLR with simulations lacking behind. Between the peaks of the values come of the distributions must be a smaller particle and the value. The distributions must be as similar as possible. I will just say that come another genetic model, already you've heard about from Mark. And you can check out the paper and also the original paper will have some more insight about it. I want to give some more time to describe the data sets that we are using. This is an exploratory work and we limit ourselves to only read a shift galaxies and we take a single bad image trying to understand whether our method works. The difference time we use images coming from the simulation. In particular I want to mention that the first simulations that we were able to produce for morphologies, it was published a couple of years ago improving on the physics. In particular, but has a sandbox as Illustris. It is of the same physics but a high revolution. We will be able to probe what they are physical model has better morphologies and also whether an improved resolution results. The results are in the paper and I will give you a couple of them come of the highlights. I just want to clarify that what you are really seeing here, the small-scale morphologies of TNG and Illustris. The simulations where -- I'm sure you all appreciate that this is a simulation and for the next spot they will come in the future. This is the main result of the paper I would say. Here you have the large distributions of our data sets. You see that illustrious and magenta, how it has the smallest and value. Which means this is the best simulation of the one that we are comparing it to. Here what we are seeing is that improving the physics with TNG is better, I mean and terms of the morphology and then the resolution with the morphology. However, it is not zero. As you see it is quite substantially below zero. There must be something to improve. What I'm going to show you here is an example to interpret these results. Here you have the size mass relation and it is color-coded. You see here that brighter colors means the galaxy ends up being better in terms of the morphology. One interesting thing for the simulation, star-forming galaxies which are the most extended ones, these particular ones, they always have the best morphologies of the simulation, as opposed to quench galaxies, they have this dark color which signal that there is a problem with the morphologies of those galaxies. I want to show you the same thing for the index eyes relation. We find that also concentrated galaxies have the same problem. We find that basically in this simulation a small-scale morphologies are small, concentrated, and quench galaxies do not agree well with observations. What is the reason, why is it like this? Ultimately this will convince you that, are astrology seems to work. If you look at the left here, the left column you see the galaxies and you see that it's very hard to put the human eye to tell them apart. You wouldn't be able to say which one is real and which ones are simulated. No problem. Instead if you go on the right to call lump you will see that some of the very strong signal in the pixel contribution to these metrics that we have, the LLR is very strong that signal from the galaxy. For some at

least of the galaxy, which implies that the center regions of these galaxies are not so well produced. A possible answer for this is the resolution. Of course you only have so much computing power and so you can't resolve so much gravitational interaction. There is a limitation, for example, but also this can be due to the physics that is implemented in there and this is completely open to explore this in detail in the future. I just want to complete by giving you future prospects and particular the Roman telescopes. We will be going deep and wide, so we are not going to have the limitation of trying to have the candles. Here we have, we will have a really angular resolution for a lot of galaxy in spirit here we are not talking only about big data. It's not only a lot of galaxies, it's a lot of complexity that we are going to see. This is an incredible challenge for the next generation of simulations. And in fact with all of the galaxy, we will be able to pin down whether simulations reproduce morphologies. We will be able to see for example, okay, something is going wrong, why? And we can also calibrate, perhaps they simulations using galaxy morphologies. They can be picked up. And also of course we can use the same approach as Mark, but as he just showed you in his talk about using this for unsupervised anomaly detection in a similar way. In summary, I've shown you that we have set up an unsupervised learning framework that is able to compare sets of images. It goes beyond parametric and nonparametric morphologies. We have found that the small-scale stellar morphologies of galaxies and Hydro simulations have improved, but they are still tensions that need to be addressed. And obviously the Roman telescope will give us an unprecedented amount of data that simulations, and especially the morphology simulations will have to be tested. Again, that is our paper and please drop me an email, chat with me on slack if you want to talk more. I'm very happy to take questions now. Thank you.

Thank you very much. I have a question. If I understood correctly you were saying that you better cover the galaxies for the quenched, early type galaxies which are harder to recover the morphologies. Do you think that could connect to the fact that the early type galaxies have both spiral and elliptical inside their stratification, let's say and can generate confusion?

That's a good question. Here we are just, here we are taking, and every pixel of this plot we have the LLR of the simulation and observation. We are not making any turn. This is really, this plot doesn't know anything about, for example, the ratio which is what you were referring to basically. This is just the pure size of the galaxy. Yeah. Does that answer?

Thank you very much for this interesting talk. Please have a look at slack after. We will like to thank all of the speakers of today and the audience. I'm going to pass it over to Max.

Max: I would like to thank Arianna. Thank you for running the session. Thanks to all the speakers again and thanks to all for your patience as we obviously had a few technical issues which we will be working on over the break. We will take a break here. We will be back at 12:30 p.m. Eastern time. That's about 40 minutes from now, less than 40 minutes. We will be doing troubleshooting. You may see the broadcast stop and restart as we try to get the streaming working again. Disregard that. Thanks again. We will see you all in 40 minutes.

Live captioning was provided by CaptionMax. Some formatting and light editing was included by the Local Organizing Committee for added clarity, but there was no attempt to correct all live captioning errors.

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